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**A STUDY OF DEPRESSION IN RELATION TO SELF-EFFICACY AND
PARENTING STYLES OF ADOLESCENTS**

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Abstract:

The present study has tried to explore depression in relation to self-efficacy & parenting style of adolescence. The term 'depression' covers a variety of negative moods and behavior change. Self-Efficacy is one of the important self related cognition, which relates to the individual's sense of personal efficacy to produce and regular events of their life. Parenting is complex activity that includes many specific behavior that work individually and together to influence child outcomes.

Keywords: *Depression, Self-Efficacy, Parenting style and Adolescent.*

Introduction:

Education is as old as human race. It is a never ending process of inner growth and development and its period stretches from cradle to the grave Education, real sense, is to humanize and to make life progressive, cultured and civilized. Education has also led to technological advancement which has in turn lead to more complexities in life. When the internal needs of human beings oppose external demands, conflicts arise in mind. This creates tension,

frustration and sometimes maladjustment in the individual. If this situation continues, it produces depression. No one can expect to go through life without some emotional tension. Mental disturbances brought about by emotional upsets result in decreased mental efficiency. Under stress the person is unstable and unpredictable and his performance is inconsistent. Depression is one of the emotional stresses common in people.

The term 'depression' covers a variety of negative moods and behavior change. Some are normal mood fluctuations and others meet the definition of clinical problems. The mood change may be temporary or long-lasting. It may range from a relatively minor feeling of melancholy to a deeply negative view of the world and an inability to function effectively.

Depression is a "whole-body" illness, involving body, mood and thoughts. The symptoms of depression may vary from person to person, and also depend on the severity of the depression. Depression causes changes in thinking, feeling, behavior, and physical well-being.

Depressive disorders come in different forms. There are several different diagnosis for depression, mostly determine by the intensity of the symptoms and specific causes of the symptoms, if that is known. The major factors of depression are Biological factors, heredity, age, life event, lack of social support etc.

Self-Efficacy is one of the important self related cognition, which relates to the individual's sense of personal efficacy to produce and regular events of their life. Self-efficacy beliefs are not fixed acts or simply a matter of knowing what to do. Self-efficacy also helps people in exercising control over events that affect their lives.

Parenting is complex activity that includes many specific behavior that work individually and together to influence child outcomes. The construct of parenting style is used to capture normal variation in parent's attempt to control and socialize their children (Baumrind 1991). Although the parents may differ in socialize their children and the extent to which they do so, it is assumed that the primary role of all parents is to influence, teach and control their children. Parenting style has been found to predict child well-being in the domains of social competence, academic performance, psychological development and problem behavior.

Attitude of parents towards their children is an important factor. The parent may reject the child, develops feeling of insecurity, helplessness and loneliness, lack of affection, and rejection of child contributes towards his frustration and maladjustment. Over protection also puts the child in to the trouble in social environment. Sometimes parents are more ambitious and set high goals for children in disregards of their physical and mental abilities which create depression in child. The present study has certain relevance in the field of education.

Objectives:

- To Study the scores of depression of male and female adolescents.
- To study the scores of self-efficacy of male and female adolescents.
- To study the impact of parenting styles on male and female adolescents.
- To find out the relationship between depression and self-efficacy of male and female adolescents.
- To find out the relationship between depression and parenting styles of male and female adolescents.
- To compare the depression scores of male and female adolescents.
- To compare the self-efficacy scores of male and female adolescents.
- To compare the parenting styles scores of male and female adolescents.

Hypothesis of the study:

- There were no significant relationship between self-efficacy and depression of adolescents.
- There were no significant relationship between depression and parenting styles of adolescents.
- There were no significant differences between the scores of male and female adolescents on depression.
- There were no significant differences between the scores of male and female adolescents on self-efficacy.
- There were no significant differences between the scores of male and female adolescents on parenting styles.

Methods & Procedure:

Sampling: For the purpose of research, simple random method of sampling will be used. A sample of 100 adolescents between ages 14-18 years, consisting of 100 students will be drawn from two senior secondary schools of Karnal. The sample will include 50 male adolescents and 50 female adolescents.

Tools Used:

- Child Depression Inventory (CDI) by Kovacs,1981
- Self-efficacy questionnaire for children (SEQ-C) by Muris, Peter,2002
- Parental Authority questionnaire-Revised (PAQ-R) by Reitman, D at al,2002

Statistical technique used:

In order to test the significant of mean differences in male and female adolescent on all the measures 't' test was applied. The correlation among the variable was obtained by using Person's product moment method.

Analysis & Interpretation:

Table no 1

List of variable with code name

Sr.no	Name of variable	code name
1	Depression	DEP
2	Self-Efficacy	SE
3	Academic Self-Efficacy	ASE
4	Social Self-Efficacy	SSE
5	Emotional Self-Efficacy	ESE
6	Authoritarian Parenting style	AP
7	Authoritative parenting style	AUP
8	Permissive Parenting Style	PP
9	Parenting Style	PS

TABLE NO 2

An overview of Mean scores of Depression of Adolescent

Sr.no	Variable	Mean score of male adolescent	mean score of Female adolescent	Total score
1	DEP	11.7	12.9	12.3

The present table indicates that the subjects in the study experience quiet moderate level of depression.

TABLE NO 3

An overview of Mean scores of Self-Efficacy of Adolescent

Sr no	Variable	Mean scores of Male adolescent	Mean score of Female adolescent	total Mean score of Adolescent
1	ASE	14.03	11.59	12.81
2	SSE	10.24	9.83	10.03
3	ESE	16.33	10.76	13.54
4	SE	13.53	10.72	24.26

The table reflects that the male have better self-efficacy (13.53) than female (10.72) adolescent.

TABLE NO 4

An overview of Mean scores of Parenting styles of Adolescent

Sr.no	variable	Mean score of male adolescent	mean score of Female adolescent	Total score
1	AP	7.8	16.26	12.03
2	AUP	13.69	9.58	11.13
3	PP	15,68	9.23	12.45
4	PS	12.39	11.69	24.08

The table shows that as the mean score of three different scales indicates that authoritarian parenting style and permissive parenting style is much better in compression to authoritarian parenting style.

TABLE NO 5

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEPRESSION AND SELF-EFFICACY

Variable	DEP	SE	ASE	SSE	ESE
DEP		-0.42	-0.23	-0.32	-0.47
SE			0.73	0.81	0.77

ASE				56	0.49
SSE					0.58
ESE					

$r = 0.14$ Significant at 0.5 Level.

$r = 0.18$ Significant at 0.1 Level.

A correlation of inter correlation matrix reveals that all the three measures of self- efficacy correlates negative with measure of depression. The correlation values between depression and ASE($r = -0.23, < 0.01$) SEE and DPE ($r = -0.32 < 0.01$),ESE and DEP ($r = -0.47 < 0.1$) and between SE and DEP ($r = -0.42 < 0.01$) . it indicates that all the measures of self – efficacy are inversely related to depression. These also imply that increase that increase in self – efficacy may decrease experience in adolescence.

TABLE NO 6

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEPRESSION AND PARENTING STYLE

Variable	DEP	AP	AUP	PP
DEP	-	0.38	-0.1	-0.43
AP			0.28	0.1
AUP		-		0.45
PP				-

The result in table no 6 shows that measures of parenting style have significant correlated with measures of depression. Authoritarian parenting style is positive (+ve) and permissive parenting style is negatively correlated with depression. Results show that increases in experience of depression but increase in permissive parenting style decreases feeling of depression.

TABLE NO 7

**SIGNIFICANT OF DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE DEPRESSION
 SCORES OF MALE & FEMALE ADOLESCENT**

Sr no	Variable	Male adolescent		Female Adolescent		t- ratio	significance level
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1	DEP	12.9	2.1	11.7	2.4	2.7	significant

The table shows that the value of t- ratio being 2.7 is significant at 0.05 level at 98 df. This shows that male adolescent s differ than female adolescent.

TABLE NO 8
SIGNIFICANT OF DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE SELF- EFFICACY SCORES OF
MALE & FEMALE ADOLESCENT

Sr no	Variable	Male adolescent		Female Adolescent		t- ratio	significance level
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1	ASE	14.03	6.40	11.59	6.10	1.5	Insignificant
2	SSE	17.00	10.24	9.83	6.02	3.4	significant
3	ESE	16.33	7.76	10.76	5.62	3.13	significant
4	SE	16.35	6.21	9.03	5.17	4.37	significant

Table reveals that in self- efficacy score the compared group significant differ to each other on SEQ. In self -efficacy the value of t- ratio being 4.37 is significant at 0.05 level of significant at 98 df. . This shows that male & female adolescent differ on SE. in three measures of self – efficacy two are significant.

TABLE NO 9
SIGNIFICANT OF DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE SELF- EFFICACY SCORES OF
MALE & FEMALE ADOLESCENT

Sr no	Variable	Male adolescent		Female Adolescent		t- ratio	significant level
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
1	AP	7.8	5.26	16.26	7.01	1.5	significant
2	AUP	13.69	5.47	9.58	5.5	3.17	significant
3	PP	15.68	4.67	9.23	5.49	3.84	significant

Table shows that on parenting styles the compared groups significant differ to each other on PAQ-R. In authoritarian parenting style the values of t- ratio being 1.5 is significant at 0.05

level at 98 df. In authoritative parenting style and permissive parenting style the value of t- ratio being 3.17 & 3.84 are significant at 0.05 level.

Significance of the Study:

The last decade has seen a steady rise of reports like desperation and recklessness among adolescents. Childhood and adolescence are critical windows of opportunity for setting down the essentials of self-efficacy that govern their lives. There are several lacunas and pit-falls in the present society. Depression is their most common problem and it interferes with normal life. It is the crucial problem of emotional and behavioral disorder. In this age of scientific and technological advancements, every person wants to excel in this competent world and when he/she fails to fulfill his/her ambitions; he/she becomes depressive and fearful especially in adolescence age because it is the period of stress and strain. It is also called the most difficult period of life. In this period because of certain physical changes, lack of confidence and maladjustment in school, home, the child's depressive level is at its peak. Moreover, in this period, there is dynamics of emotions. The students worry about being successful in their studies, getting to school on time, mastering their lessons, obtaining good marks in report cards. They are anxious about their relationship with their teachers, parents, brothers and fellows. In schools, students face problems like inability to pay attention, day -dreaming, jumping in to self-consciousness and acting without thinking. Self-efficacy plays a key role in the etiology and maintenance of affective disorder.

Attitude of parents towards their children is an important factor. The parents may reject the child. The rejected child develops feelings of insecurity, helplessness and loneliness. Lack of affection and rejection of child contributes towards his frustration and maladjustment. Over-protection also puts the child in to trouble in social environment. Sometimes parents are ambitious and set high goals for their children in disregard of their physical and mental abilities which create depression in adolescents.

Bandura et al. (1999) analyzed how different facts of perceived self-efficacy operate in concert with in a network of socio-cognitive influence in childhood depression. Perceived social and academic inefficacy contributed to concurrent and subsequent depression both directly and

through their impact on academic achievement, prosocialness and problem behaviors. In the shorter run, children were depressed over beliefs of their academic inefficacy rather than over their actual academic performances. In the longer run, the impact of a low sense of academic efficacy on depression was mediated through academic achievement, problem behavior, and prior depression. Perceived social inefficacy had a heavier impact on depression in girls than in boys in the longer term. Depression was also more strongly linked over time for girls than for boys.

Thus, it is significant to know how self-efficacy and parenting style influence the depression. Keeping all these views in her mind, the researcher selected the problem for the purpose of study.

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